

Vocabulary in The First Language and Written Communication Skills of Grade Two Learners

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Abstract. The general purpose of this study was to look into the relationship between the vocabulary in the first language and the written communication skills of grade 2 learners. This study made use of the quasi experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Maibo Elementary School, Magsaysay South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 89 grade two pupils – 45 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 44 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of vocabulary has increased the vocabulary in the first language and written communication skills of grade two learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. Vocabulary in the First Language
2. Written Communication skills
3. homogeneous

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1. Introduction

Enriching vocabulary in the first language is a challenge to the early Grades teachers in the macro skill development on a step-to-step basis cursive form since stroke and hand exercises cannot be done during this pandemic but then online videos help the teaching-learning process with the proper guidance of both parents and teachers that conveys understanding on written and oral communication. Vocabulary plays important role in language learning. Vocabulary is also an essential skill for learning to read, speak, write and listen. Without sufficient vocabulary, people cannot communicate and express their feeling both in form of 70 spoken and written effectively. The more people master vocabulary the more they can speak, write, read and listen as they want. Without grammar very little can be conveyed; without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed. It means that even someone has good grammar but it will be useless if they do not know many vocabularies (Wilkins in Thornbury, 2019). In addition, vocabulary is one of important things to be taught in learning foreign language because it will be impossible to

speak up without variety of words (Ur, 2020). This study revealed that problems or difficulties faced by the students in vocabulary learning were various. The difficulties faced by the students were almost all of the students have difficulties in pronouncing the words, how to write and spell, the different grammatical form of a word known as inflections was one of causes of student's difficulties in learning vocabulary. In addition, the students found difficulties in choosing the appropriate meaning of the words and also still confuse in using the word based on the context. The last, the students are also still confusing when they found words or expression that are idiomatic. In Singapore, a research study examining vocabulary challenges among students in Singapore revealed a range of factors that contribute to these difficulties. These factors include limited exposure to diverse linguistic environments, socioeconomic circumstances, bilingualism, inadequate utilization of strategic vocabulary learning methods, and the potential advantages of digital tools in enhancing vocabulary skills (Tan, 2019). In the Philippines, the acquisition of vocabulary in one's first language is the utmost importance for facilitating successful communication and achieving academic excellence. Numerous research has been undertaken to ascertain and mitigate the challenges encountered by Filipino students in the process of acquiring and enhancing their vocabulary. A study on the vocabulary acquisition and retention of Filipino pupils revealed the difficulties encountered by Filipino learners in developing their vocabulary in their first language. Common challenges include limited exposure to vocabulary, socioeconomic factors, ineffective learning strategies, and a lack of resources. However, the studies provide valuable insights into potential solutions, such as integrating multimedia materials, encouraging extensive reading, and employing effective instructional strategies (Reyes, 2021). In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Maibo Elementary School, learners could barely express first language vocabularies in written communication. The researcher being a teacher in the above stated school finds it appropriate and timely to conduct this study to propose a plan of action that would explore other dimensions in solving the merging problem.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher's method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has accessed to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

2.2. Research Respondents—This study conducted in Maibo Elementary School, Magsaysay South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 89 grade two pupils – 45 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 44 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made

$O_1 \quad x \quad O_2$

$O_3 \quad x \quad O_4$

Where:

- O_1 - Pretest of the experimental group
- O_2 - Posttest of the experimental group
- O_3 - Pretest of the controlled group
- O_4 - Posttest of the controlled group
- - Non-random assignment of subjects
- X - Treatment applied in the experimental group

Distribution of Respondents

	Subjects	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	45
2	Section B	44
	Total	89

use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It was a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learners online for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 25 –item test will eventually determine the written communica-

tion skills of the research subjects. The pretest will be administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest will be very helpful to assess the written communication skills of the grade two learners. On the other hand, post test will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the written communication skills of the grade two learners, the following continuum will be used based on DepEd rating system..

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Sur, Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V and the School Principal of Maibo Elementary School. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of

the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Maibo Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

Interval Scale Level Criteria

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean will be used to describe the written communication skills of the grade two learners. Eta square will be used to measure the magnitude of effect of vocabulary in the first language on the written communication skills of the grade two learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade two learners. The controlled group got the mean of 24.3 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 25.5 or Beginning.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	45	24.3	Beginning
Experimental Group	44	25.5	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Ur (1996) who said that that without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed. It means that even someone has good grammar but it will be useless if they do not know many vocabularies (Ur, 1996) Vocabulary plays important role in language learning. Vocabulary is also an essential skill for learning to read, speak, write and listen. Without sufficient vocabulary, people cannot communicate and express their feeling both in form of 70 spoken and written effectively. The more people master vocabulary the more they can speak, write, read and listen as they want. Without grammar very little can be conveyed; without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed. It means that even someone has good grammar but it will be useless if they do not know many vocabularies (Wilkins in Thornbury, 2019)

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	45	36.2	80.4	Developing Proficiency
Experimental Group	44	39.3	87.3	Approaching Proficiency

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade two learners. The controlled group got the mean of 36.2 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 39.3 or Approaching. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has

a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 13.8 from a mean rating of 25.5 to 39.3. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Tan (2019) who cited that a range of factors that contribute to these difficulties. These factors include limited exposure to diverse linguistic environments, socioeconomic circumstances, bilingualism, inadequate utilization of strategic vocabulary learning methods, and the potential advantages of digital tools in enhancing vocabulary skills (Tan, 2019). Vo-

cabulary having a strong and wide range is of the utmost importance for students, during their college years and in subsequent stages of their academic and professional lives. The acquisition and utilization of vocabulary are fundamental to proficient communication and significantly contribute to achieving academic success. The possession of a broad vocabulary by pupils enhances their ability to comprehend complex materials, communicate their thoughts with preciseness, and actively participate in meaningful discussions (Beglar, 2020).

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	39	-5.40	.0343	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.40 with a p-value of .0343 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade two learners. This implies that the used of vocabulary in the first language and written communication skills of grade two learners have contributed the effectiveness in teaching the subject which is revealed by the scores of the grade two learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Baumann (2019) who said that the acquisition and utilization of vocabulary serves as the fundamental basis for comprehending and expressing oneself in language. It facili-

tates persons in comprehending and efficiently conveying meaning. An extensive vocabulary contributes to the development of reading comprehension, writing proficiency, and overall linguistic proficiency (Baumann, 2019). Having a strong and wide vocabulary is of utmost importance for students during their college years and in subsequent stages of their academic and professional lives. The acquisition and utilization of vocabulary are fundamental to proficient communication and significantly contribute to achieving academic success. The possession of a broad vocabulary by pupils enhances their ability to comprehend complex materials, communicate their thoughts with preciseness, and actively participate in meaningful discussions (Beglar, 2020).

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Grade 6 Students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
89	-4.21	0.324	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of vocabulary in the first language and written communication approach on the communication skills of grade two learners. It generated an Eta² value of 0.324 which signifies large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in teaching grade two learners to capture the interest of the learners. Teaching Vocabulary plays important role in language learning. Vocabulary is also an essential skill for learning to read, speak, write and listen. The acquisition of vocabulary is a fundamental component of language acquisition and serves a crucial function in strengthening one's proficiency in communi-

cating The process of increasing one's vocabulary contributes to improved levels of understanding when engaging with written material. The ownership of a wide vocabulary by students facilitates their comprehension of the complex details and delicate subtleties included in written texts, thereby enabling them to derive profound meaning from the material. Moreover, a strong vocabulary enables pupils to effectively express their ideas with more accuracy, both in written works and during oral discussions. The skill of effective self-expression is widely valued in academic institutions and diverse work environments (Chung, 2021).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of vocabulary in the first language and written communication skills approach of grade two learners.

4.1. Findings—This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Maibo Elementary School, Magsaysay South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 89 grade two pupils – 45 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 44 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of vocabulary has increased the vocabulary in the first language

and written communication skills of grade two learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade two learners both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group are at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the approaching level.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching grade two learners should use vocabulary in the first language and written communication skills as a strategy that would further enrich vocabulary in the first language. Teaching young learners, particularly those in grade two, is a critical phase in their educational journey. At

this stage, students are developing foundational skills that will support their academic growth and lifelong learning. One effective strategy that teachers can employ is the integration of first language (L1) vocabulary alongside developing written communication skills in the target language. Developing vocabulary in a first language and honing written communication skills are essential strategies for enhancing overall literacy and communication proficiency. The school heads should promote the use of vocabulary in the first language and written communication skills approach as a strategy that would engage the child actively in the learning process as it is revealed in the study that difficulties faced by the students in vocabulary learning were various. The difficulties faced by the students were almost all of the students have difficulties in pronouncing the words, how to write and spell, the different grammatical form of a

word known as inflections was one of causes of student's difficulties in learning vocabulary. . A school policy about the utilization of vocabulary in the first language and written communication skills approach can be issued. Besides, utilization of vocabulary in the first language and written communication skills are interconnected areas that significantly influence one's ability to express ideas effectively. He can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session using the approach as a strategy in teaching and propose a plan of action that would explore other dimensions in solving the merging problem. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of vocabulary in the first language and written communication skills approach as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

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